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Impact of Political Interference on Recruitment Process and Employee Performance: A Study of the Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of political interference on the recruitment process and employee performance in Federal Polytechnic, Offa. The objective was to determine how political influence affects meritocracy, fairness, transparency, and efficiency in public institutional recruitment. Merit System Theory was adopted. The study population of this study was 635 while a sample size of 240 was derived using the Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula but 227 valid responses were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Findings revealed that 66.1% of respondents agreed that political interference undermines fairness and credibility in recruitment, while 69.6% believed recruitment processes are manipulated to favour politically connected individuals. The study further revealed that 64.7% of respondents believed political interference reduces transparency and accountability, while 83.3% agreed that merit-based recruitment enhances productivity and

efficiency. Although teamwork appeared relatively unaffected (63.5% disagreed that political recruitment disrupts cooperation), political interference was still identified as a major impediment to institutional performance and service delivery. The study recommended that the Governing Council and Human Resource Department institutionalize a transparent, merit-based recruitment framework; the Ministry of Tertiary Education and the Office of the Head of Service enforce existing recruitment regulations to minimize undue influence; and the Rectory ensure administrative autonomy in recruitment decisions.

Keywords: Political interference, recruitment, meritocracy, employee performance, Federal Polytechnic Offa.

Introduction

The recruitment and selection of personnel in public institutions are guided by principles of merit, competence, transparency, and fairness, ensuring that qualified individuals are employed to deliver effective public service. In many developed countries, the recruitment process is institutionalized through civil service commissions or independent bodies that uphold objectivity and professionalism. The effectiveness of such systems contributes significantly to employee motivation, institutional performance, and national development (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020; OECD, 2019). However, where political influence overrides established procedures, it often undermines organizational efficiency and productivity (Poocharoen & Brillantes, 2013).

In Africa, political interference in recruitment remains a major governance challenge that threatens institutional integrity and performance. The public sector, in particular, often suffers from undue political control, where appointments and promotions are based on political patronage rather than merit. This practice weakens administrative competence, erodes public trust, and results in low employee morale and inefficiency (Aye, 2016; Mutahaba, 2017). Studies in countries such as Kenya, Ghana, and South Africa have

shown that politically motivated recruitment contributes to corruption, poor service delivery, and high staff turnover in public institutions (Munzhedzi, 2016; Asiedu & Folitse, 2020).

In Nigeria, political interference in public service recruitment has become a persistent problem that undermines the principles of fairness, accountability, and professionalism. Despite the establishment of regulatory bodies and civil service reforms aimed at promoting merit-based recruitment, political influence continues to dictate who gets employed, especially in government-owned organizations and educational institutions (Ifaka & Odigie, 2021). This has led to the employment of unqualified personnel, limited job satisfaction, low productivity, and weak institutional performance (Eneanya, 2018; Ezeani, 2020). Consequently, the efficiency of the Nigerian public sector remains below expectations (Okon & Obot, 2022).

Polytechnics and other tertiary institutions have not been exempted from these challenges. The recruitment of academic and non-academic staff is often influenced by political connections rather than competence and qualifications. This trend has adverse implications for employee performance, institutional reputation, and the overall quality of education (Nwachukwu, Achori, Pepple, & Nchey-Achukwu, 2019; Ogunode, 2024). When political interference determines staff recruitment, it discourages merit-based competition, lowers morale among qualified employees, and fosters inefficiency and lack of accountability (Okoro & Fernandez, 2024).

In Federal Polytechnic, Offa, as in many other public tertiary institutions in Nigeria, recruitment and personnel management are critical to achieving organizational goals and ensuring effective service delivery. However, anecdotal evidence and staff perceptions suggest that political interference has affected the fairness and transparency of recruitment processes. Such interference can lead to favouritism, poor staff motivation, and reduced productivity. Against this background, this study will examine the impact of political interference on the

recruitment process and employee performance in the Federal Polytechnic.

Statement of the Problem

Despite regulatory frameworks and civil-service reforms meant to safeguard meritocratic recruitment, anecdotal reports and sector studies suggest that political actors still exert influence over hiring decisions in many public institutions (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020; OECD, 2019). At Federal Polytechnic, Offa, stakeholders have expressed concerns that recruitment decisions may be affected by external political pressures and patronage networks. Such interference may compromise the quality of teaching, research, and administrative support with negative consequences for staff performance and institutional outputs. This trend poses a risk to institutional integrity, reduces morale among qualified staff, and compromises the Polytechnic's mission of delivering quality technical education (Ifaka & Odigie, 2021; Ogunode, 2024). Politically influenced recruitment may lead to the employment of unqualified or less-committed personnel, resulting in poor job performance, inefficiency, and reduced accountability. Employees who perceive unfair recruitment practices may also become demotivated, leading to poor teamwork, conflict, and low productivity (Okoro & Fernandez, 2024). Many scholars have studied on recruitment such as Nwachukwu, Achori, Gogo and Nchey-Achukwu (2019); Muna, Azam and Albattat (2022); Oyadiran, Ishaq and Agunbiade (2023), but none have written on the impact of political interference in recruitment at Federal Polytechnic, Offa. This study intends to fill the gap.

Empirical Review

Nwachukwu, Achori, Gogo and Nchey-Achukwu (2019) investigated the interference of politicians in the recruitment and selection of academic staff in federal polytechnics in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The findings revealed that political interference leads to the appointment of unqualified individuals to academic positions, thereby undermining

meritocracy and diminishing educational standards. The study emphasized that the quality of graduates is directly linked to the competence of academic staff, and that political involvement in recruitment processes contributes to declining institutional performance. The study recommended that tertiary institutions within the region should discourage political interference and uphold transparent, merit-based recruitment systems. Ensuring that only qualified and competent academic personnel are appointed would enhance institutional credibility and improve the academic outcomes of polytechnics in the Niger Delta.

Anayochukwu and Ani (2021) investigated the impact of political interference on personnel management in local governments across Nigeria. A quantitative research design was adopted. The findings revealed that constitutional ambiguities in Nigeria's federal structure encourage state officials to exert undue control over local government administration. Consequently, the study highlighted that such political involvement contributes to inefficiency and poor performance within local government systems. The study recommended the need to strengthen institutional frameworks to safeguard local government autonomy, ensure merit-based recruitment and promotion, and establish transparent human resource management practices free from political manipulation.

Ifaka and Odigie (2021) examined the effect of political interference on bureaucratic performance in Nigeria. The study adopted a mixed-methods research design. The study revealed that approximately 86% of employees recruited into DESOPADEC were selected through politically influenced processes rather than merit-based criteria. Such interference has severely constrained the organization's ability to attract and retain skilled and qualified personnel, resulting in weakened bureaucratic performance and diminished institutional credibility. The study recommended insulating bureaucratic recruitment and selection

processes from political influence by involving private sector consultants, host community representatives, and civil society organizations in the recruitment process. Also, the use of information and communication technology (ICT) tools to facilitate transparent interviews and ensure equal opportunity for all candidates.

Muna, Azam and Albattat (2022) examined the impact of political influence on recruitment and selection practices within the Civil Service of the Maldives using a quantitative research design. The findings revealed that political leaders often use their authority to influence recruitment decisions by favouring friends, relatives, or loyal associates. The study concluded that fair and transparent recruitment and selection practices are essential for improving employee satisfaction and enhancing the quality of public service. The study recommended that human resources practitioners, policy makers, and civil service administrators adopt merit-oriented recruitment systems and strengthen institutional mechanisms to minimize political interference.

Oyadiran, Ishaq and Agunbiade (2023) examined the effects of recruitment and selection processes on organisational performance, focusing on the influence of job analysis, interviews, hiring policies, and testing procedures. The study relied on secondary data. Findings revealed a significant positive relationship between effective recruitment and selection practices and organisational performance. The study recommended that management should prioritise merit-based recruitment rather than relying on personal relationships or social affiliations.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts Merit System Theory propounded by Dwight Waldo (1948) and later developed by Frederick C. Mosher (1968) and Nigro and Kellough (2006), The theory emphasizes that public sector recruitment and personnel management should be based on merit,

competence, and qualifications rather than political affiliation, favoritism, or nepotism. The assumptions of the Merit System Theory include the belief that employment decisions should be determined by merit and competence, that recruitment must be impartial and transparent, and that all qualified individuals should have equal access to job opportunities in the public service. The theory further assumes that merit-based recruitment fosters accountability, integrity, and performance, while also promoting job satisfaction and institutional efficiency. When recruitment is influenced by political considerations, it undermines these assumptions, leading to inefficiency, low morale, and corruption within public institutions.

The theory is relevant to this study because it lies in its capacity to explain how political interference negatively affects recruitment processes and employee performance. In the context of the Federal Polytechnic, Offa, political influence in employment decisions can distort merit-based procedures, resulting in the selection of unqualified personnel who may not effectively contribute to organizational productivity. The Merit System Theory provides a clear lens for analysing the extent to which the principles of fairness, competence, and accountability are compromised by political manipulation. It therefore serves as a useful framework for understanding the relationship between political interference and the quality of human resource outcomes in public tertiary institutions.

The theory has attracted significant scholarly criticism for its rigidity and overemphasis on formal qualifications, which may inadvertently exclude individuals with valuable experiential knowledge and practical competence. According to Peters and Pierre (2016), meritocratic systems tend to prioritize credentials over actual performance capabilities, thereby narrowing the talent pool and discouraging innovation within public institutions. Similarly, Adebayo (2019) argues that the strict adherence to formal educational qualifications in Nigeria's public service often sidelines skilled individuals who lack

conventional certifications but possess the technical expertise needed for efficient service delivery. Furthermore, Olaopa (2020) and Ezeani (2012) observe that the Merit System Theory inadequately addresses the complex political realities prevalent in developing countries like Nigeria, where deep-rooted patronage, nepotism, and ethnic favouritism continue to influence recruitment and selection processes. In the same vein, Adamolekun (2018) contends that the bureaucratic rigidity associated with the merit system may result in prolonged recruitment processes, limited adaptability to local contexts, and inefficiencies in addressing the dynamic needs of modern public institutions.

Political Interference Theory is anchored in the politics–administration dichotomy advanced by Woodrow Wilson in (1887). Wilson argued that administrative functions, particularly personnel management and recruitment, should be insulated from partisan political influence to promote efficiency, professionalism, and neutrality in public institutions. This theoretical position laid the foundation for understanding how political intrusion into recruitment and selection processes undermines institutional effectiveness and public service delivery. The theory assumes that merit-based recruitment enhances organizational performance by ensuring that competent, qualified, and experienced individuals are selected into public service positions. It further assumes that political interference in recruitment introduces patronage, nepotism, favouritism, and godfatherism, which weaken professional standards and distort established recruitment procedures. According to the theory, politically influenced recruitment breeds inefficiency and corruption because individuals appointed through political connections often prioritize loyalty to political sponsors over organizational goals and public interest.

The theory is relevant to this study because in a federal institution like the Federal Polytechnic, Offa, recruitment processes may be influenced by national, state, or local political interests seeking to reward supporters or advance ethnic and partisan considerations. The theory

provides an analytical framework for understanding how such political dynamics affect recruitment outcomes, staff performance, and service delivery within the Polytechnic. Although Political Interference Theory has been subject to critique for over-idealizing the separation between politics and administration, many scholars acknowledge that this dichotomy highlights real risks arising from political intrusion in recruitment systems. Critics of the strict politics–administration dichotomy argue that in practice, complete neutrality is unrealistic because administrative actions inevitably intersect with political mandates and decisions (Overeem, 2012). Ibeh and Onwuzuruike (2025) found that political interference in recruitment and promotions fosters corruption, inefficiency, and declining worker performance in public organizations. Thus, despite criticisms that Political Interference Theory may oversimplify the relationship between politics and administration, its analytical value remains significant for the Federal Polytechnic, Offa. It provides insight into how political interference in recruitment processes undermines the quality of human capital and negatively impacts employee performance an issue corroborated by empirical literature on politicization and public sector capacity.

The Merit System Theory is significant, as it offers a framework for evaluating how recruitment practices at the Federal Polytechnic, Offa align with meritocratic principles. The theory guides the investigation into whether political interference has compromised objectivity in hiring decisions and how such interference affects employee morale, motivation, and overall performance. By emphasizing the need for competence-based recruitment, the theory highlights that sustainable institutional performance depends on transparent, fair, and accountable employment practices. Thus, the Merit System Theory not only provides the theoretical basis for this study but also supports policy recommendations aimed at strengthening institutional autonomy and professionalism in public personnel management.

Methodology

The population of this study was 635 drawn from Senior and Junior Establishment, Admission Office, Students Affairs, Certificate Office, Research and Development, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Examinations and Records, Internal Quality Control, Bursary, Public Relations, Pension Office, Legal Unit, Staff Training and Development, Polytechnic Consult, Entrepreneurship, Academic Planning Office, Works and Security, Health Workers, Rectorry and Council Affairs in Federal Polytechnic, Offa. The sample size was 240 derived through Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula. Out of the 240 copies of a questionnaire, two hundred and twenty-seven (227) were retrieved and analysed, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Data were analysed, using a 5-point Likert scale with “1 = Strongly Disagreed, 2 = Disagreed, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Agreed, and 5 = Strongly Agreed”.

Thus:

$$n = \frac{X^2 N P (1-P)}{e^2 (N-1) + X^2 P (1-P)}$$

$$n = \frac{3.841 \times 635 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{((0.05)^2 \times 635 - 1 + (3.841 \times 0.5 \times 0.5))}$$
$$n = 609.75875$$

$$\frac{1.585 + 0.96025}{n = 239.57}$$

Approximately n = 240

Result and Discussion

Table 6.1: Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.965	.964	11

The reliability statistics reveal a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.965, a standardized item alpha of 0.964, and a total of 11 items. This indicates a very high degree of internal consistency among the items in the instrument. Since a Cronbach’s Alpha value above 0.70 is generally considered acceptable, the obtained value of 0.965 demonstrates that the questionnaire items are strongly interrelated and measure the same underlying concept effectively. Hence, the instrument used for the study can be considered highly reliable and appropriate for data collection and subsequent analysis.

Table 6.2: Political Interference in Recruitment Process

S/N	Statement	SD n (%)	D n (%)	U n (%)	A n (%)	SA n (%)	TOTAL (N=227)	REMARK
1	Political interference affects the fairness and credibility of recruitment and selection decisions.	27 (11.9%)	47 (20.7%)	3 (1.3%)	94 (41.4%)	56 (24.7%)	227 (100%)	Agree
2	Political office holders often influence the appointment of administrative and academic staff.	32 (14.1%)	51 (22.5%)	2 (0.9%)	85 (37.4%)	57 (25.1%)	227 (100%)	Agree
3	Recruitment exercises in the Polytechnic are often manipulated to favour politically connected individuals.	24 (10.6%)	43 (18.9%)	2 (0.9%)	103 (45.4%)	55 (24.2%)	227 (100%)	Agree
4	The recruitment policy of the institution is not strictly based on merit and competence.	34 (15%)	47 (20.7%)	4 (4.8%)	90 (39.6%)	52 (22.9%)	227 (100%)	Agree
5	The recruitment process lacks transparency due to external political pressure.	32 (14.1%)	39 (17.2%)	9 (4%)	99 (43.6%)	48 (21.1%)	227 (100%)	Agree
5	The recruitment process lacks transparency due to external political pressure.	32 (14.1%)	39 (17.2%)	9 (4%)	99 (43.6%)	48 (21.1%)	227 (100%)	Agree
5	The recruitment process lacks transparency due to external political pressure.	32 (14.1%)	39 (17.2%)	9 (4%)	99 (43.6%)	48 (21.1%)	227 (100%)	Agree

Researchers’ Field Survey 2025

Table 2 presents respondents’ views on political interference in the recruitment process within the institution. The analysis shows that a majority of respondents agreed that political influence has a significant negative effect on the fairness, transparency, and merit-based nature of recruitment and selection. Most respondents (66.1%) agreed that political interference undermines the fairness and credibility of recruitment and selection decisions, while 62.5% believed that political office holders often influence the appointment of administrative and academic staff. About 69.6% of respondents observed that recruitment exercises are frequently manipulated to favour politically connected individuals. Similarly, 62.5% agreed that the recruitment policy of the

institution is not strictly based on merit and competence, and 64.7% believed that the recruitment process lacks transparency due to external political pressure.

Table 6.3: Impact on Employee Performance

S/N	Statement	SD n (%)	D n (%)	U n (%)	A n (%)	SA n (%)	TOTAL (N=227)	REMARK
1	Employees recruited through political influence often lack the required skills and qualifications for their positions.	14 (6.2%)	45 (19.8%)	3 (1.3%)	95 (41.9%)	70 (30.8%)	227 (100%)	Agree
2	Merit-based recruitment promotes higher productivity and organizational efficiency.	17 (7.5%)	15 (6.6%)	6 (2.6%)	96 (42.3%)	93 (41%)	227 (100%)	Agree
2	Political interference in recruitment reduces staff morale and motivation in the workplace.	32 (14.1%)	43 (18.9%)	2 (0.9%)	94 (41.4%)	56 (24.7%)	227 (100%)	Agree
4	The presence of politically recruited employees affects teamwork and cooperation among staff.	46 (20.3%)	98 (43.2%)	9 (4%)	62 (27.3%)	12 (5.3%)	227 (100%)	Disagree
5	Political interference in recruitment leads to poor service delivery institutional inefficiency.	25 (11%)	46 (20.3%)	3 (1.3%)	98 (43.2%)	55 (24.2%)	227 (100%)	Agree
6	Minimizing political influence in the recruitment process will enhance employee commitment and performance at the Polytechnic.	23 (10.1%)	45 (19.8%)	3 (1.3%)	95 (41.9%)	61 (26.9%)	227 (100%)	Agree

Researchers’ Field Survey 2025

Table 3 presents respondents’ opinions on the impact of political interference on employee performance within the institution. The analysis reveals that a majority of respondents agreed that political influence in recruitment negatively affects employee competence, morale, and overall institutional performance. Most respondents (72.7%) agreed that employees recruited through political influence often lack the necessary skills and qualifications for their positions. A large proportion (83.3%) agreed that merit-based recruitment promotes higher productivity and organizational efficiency. Likewise, 66.1% of respondents agreed that political interference in recruitment reduces staff morale and motivation in the workplace. However, responses to

the statement on teamwork and cooperation among staff were mixed, as 63.5% disagreed that the presence of politically recruited employees affects teamwork, indicating that this factor may have a limited impact on collaboration. In addition, 67.4% agreed that political interference in recruitment leads to poor service delivery and institutional inefficiency, while 68.8% believed that minimizing political influence in recruitment would enhance employee commitment and performance at the Polytechnic.

7. Regression

7.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics			Durbin-Watson	Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	df1	df2		
1	.933 ^a	.870	.870	.34992	.870	1510.601	.921	.921	
1	.933 ^a	.870	.870	.34992	.870	1510.601	225	.921	

a. Predictors: (Constant), POLITICAL INTERFERENCE
 b. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

a. Predictors: (Constant), POLITICAL INTERFERENCE
 b. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

The model summary presented shows the relationship between political interference and employee performance within the institution. The results reveal a strong positive correlation coefficient ($R = 0.933$), indicating a very high degree of association between political interference and employee performance. The coefficient of determination ($R\text{ Square} = 0.870$) implies that 87% of the variation in employee performance is explained by political interference, while the remaining 13% may be due to other factors not included in the model. The Adjusted R Square (0.870) confirms the robustness of the model, indicating minimal difference between the observed and adjusted

values. The standard error of the estimate (0.34992) shows a small margin of deviation, suggesting that the model predicts the dependent variable with high accuracy. The F-change value (1510.601) with a significance level of 0.000 indicates that the model is statistically significant and that political interference has a substantial impact on employee performance. The Durbin-Watson value of 0.921 suggests the presence of some positive autocorrelation in the residuals, though not severe enough to invalidate the model. Overall, the findings demonstrate that political interference significantly influences employee performance, accounting for a large proportion of its variability, and thus plays a major role in determining institutional productivity and efficiency.

7.2 ANOVA

Model	R	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Sig.
1		Regression	1	184.967		1510.601	.000 ^b
		Residual	225	.122	.127		
		Total	226	212.517	226		
a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE b. Predictors: (Constant), POLITICAL INTERFERENCE							

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

The ANOVA table presents the test of significance for the relationship between political interference and employee performance within the institution. The results show that the regression sum of squares (184.967) is substantially higher than the residual sum of squares (27.550), indicating that a large proportion of the variation in employee performance is explained by political interference. With an F-value of

1510.601 and a significance level (Sig.) of 0.000, the result is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This means that political interference has a significant effect on employee performance, and the regression model provides a good fit for the data. The very low significance value ($p < 0.05$) confirms that the relationship between political interference and employee performance is not due to chance. Overall, the ANOVA result demonstrates that political interference is a strong and statistically significant predictor of employee performance, implying that variations in recruitment influenced by political factors considerably affect how effectively employees perform their duties within the institution.

7.3 Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	1.012	.067		15.076	.000	.880	1.145
POLITICAL INTERFERENCE	.715	.018	.933	38.866	.000	.679	.751

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

The coefficients table presents the regression analysis results showing the effect of political interference on employee performance within the institution. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for political interference is 0.715 with a standard error of 0.018, and a t-value of 38.866 at a

significance level (Sig.) of 0.000. This indicates a statistically significant and positive relationship between political interference and employee performance. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.933$) further confirms that political interference has a strong predictive influence on employee performance. The positive coefficient means that as political interference increases, employee performance also changes in the same direction though in this context, it likely reflects the degree of dependence or influence rather than improvement. The 95% confidence interval (0.679–0.751) suggests that the true value of the coefficient lies within this range, further validating the precision of the estimate. Overall, the findings indicate that political interference significantly predicts changes in employee performance, accounting for a substantial portion of its variability. This implies that the extent of political influence in recruitment and personnel management strongly affects how employees perform, thereby shaping the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the institution.

7.4 Correlations

Correlations

	POLITICAL INTERFERENCE	EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	
POLITICAL INTERFERENCE	1	Pearson Correlation	1
Pearson Correlation		.933**	.000
N	227	227	227
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	.933**	.933**	1
N	227	227	227

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation result presented shows the relationship between political interference and employee performance within the institution. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.933$) indicates a very strong positive relationship between the two variables. This means that changes in political interference are strongly associated with changes in

employee performance. The significance value (Sig. = 0.000), which is less than the 0.01 threshold, confirms that the relationship is statistically significant at the 1% level. This implies that the observed correlation is not due to random chance but reflects a meaningful association between the variables.

Overall, the findings suggest that political interference has a significant and strong influence on employee performance in the institution. As political interference increases, it tends to have a corresponding effect on the performance of employees, highlighting the critical impact of political factors on institutional efficiency and staff productivity.

7.5 Histogram

The histogram displayed above illustrates the normality of residuals for the regression model where employee performance is the dependent variable. The distribution of the regression standardized residuals shows that the data are approximately normally distributed around the mean. The mean of the residuals (5.56E-15) is very close to zero, and the standard deviation (0.998) is approximately equal to one, both of which meet the assumptions of normality in regression analysis. The bell-

shaped curve superimposed on the histogram aligns closely with the bars, indicating that the residuals follow a normal distribution pattern. This result confirms that the assumption of normality has been satisfied, implying that the regression model is statistically appropriate and reliable for explaining the relationship between political interference and employee performance. Therefore, the model provides valid estimates and can be used confidently for interpretation and prediction.

Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal 66.1% of respondents believe political interference undermines fairness and credibility in recruitment supports the view of Olaopa (2019), who observed that the politicization of recruitment processes in public institutions distorts administrative professionalism and weakens the integrity of the civil service. Similarly, the finding that 62.5% of respondents acknowledged the influence of political office holders in staff appointments aligns with Nwosu and Chukwuemeka (2018), who noted that political actors often exploit recruitment exercises to reward loyalists rather than qualified candidates, thereby eroding institutional competence. The high percentage (69.6%) of respondents who indicated that recruitment exercises are manipulated to favour politically connected individuals resonates with Adewale and Jimoh (2020), who found that such favouritism leads to inefficiency, low morale, and poor service delivery in public organizations. Furthermore, the perception that the recruitment policy is not strictly based on merit and competence, as reported by 62.5% of respondents, corroborates Eneanya (2021), who argued that political pressures compromise the merit system, resulting in the appointment of unqualified individuals who lack the capacity to deliver quality performance.

Additionally, the finding that 64.7% of respondents agreed that the recruitment process lacks transparency due to political influence reflects the broader governance challenge in Nigeria's public sector. Akinwale and Olatunji (2022) emphasized that political interference weakens

institutional accountability and creates room for corruption, favouritism, and mediocrity. This lack of transparency discourages qualified applicants and reduces public confidence in the fairness of administrative processes. The findings support Weber's Bureaucratic Theory, which advocates for merit-based recruitment and a clear separation between politics and administration to ensure efficiency and professionalism. However, the current situation in the institution reflects a deviation from these principles, as political actors continue to exert undue influence over recruitment decisions. According to Okon and Ude (2021), such politicization breeds inefficiency and limits the ability of institutions to achieve organizational goals effectively.

The findings demonstrate that 72.7% of respondents acknowledged that politically recruited employees often lack the qualifications and technical expertise required for their roles. This finding corroborates the position of Adewale and Jimoh (2020), who emphasized that political favouritism in recruitment compromises the quality of personnel and reduces institutional efficiency because such individuals are often chosen based on political loyalty rather than professional merit. Furthermore, the strong agreement (83.3%) that merit-based recruitment enhances productivity and efficiency aligns with Weber's (1947) bureaucratic model, which advocates for meritocracy, competence, and rational procedures in public administration. According to Olaopa (2019), institutions that uphold merit-based employment systems tend to experience higher productivity, innovation, and staff accountability.

Conversely, when political considerations dominate recruitment, it leads to inefficiency, low morale, and stagnation in organizational growth. A notable proportion of respondents (66.1%) also agreed that political interference reduces employee morale and motivation, which is consistent with Eneanya (2021), who noted that unmerited appointments often demoralize competent staff and foster resentment in the workplace. When employees perceive that political favouritism overrides competence, it creates a sense of injustice and discourages

high performance. Okon and Ude (2021) similarly observed that political interference in recruitment contributes to organizational dissatisfaction, poor work ethics, and lack of motivation among dedicated employees.

Interestingly, the study found that teamwork was less affected by political recruitment, as 63.5% of respondents disagreed that politically recruited employees disrupt cooperation. This indicates that, despite political influence, employees may still maintain cordial relationships and collaborate effectively on institutional tasks. This finding resonates with Akinwale and Olatunji (2022), who argued that strong team culture and effective leadership can mitigate the divisive effects of political recruitment on workplace harmony. Additionally, 67.4% of respondents agreed that political interference contributes to poor service delivery and inefficiency, supporting the findings of Ogunyemi (2018), who reported that politically influenced personnel often lack the discipline and commitment required for quality performance. The majority (68.8%) further expressed that reducing political influence would enhance employee commitment and performance, reflecting a shared belief that administrative autonomy and transparency are critical for institutional improvement.

Conclusion

The study examined the impact of political interference on recruitment process and employee performance in Federal Polytechnic, Offa. The study concludes that political interference significantly undermines the recruitment process and employee performance within the institution. It reveals that favouritism and political manipulation in staff appointments compromise merit, fairness, and transparency, leading to the employment of unqualified individuals who hinder institutional efficiency. Such interference lowers employee morale, weakens professionalism, and erodes public trust in the system.

Recommendations

The Institution should institutionalize a merit-based recruitment system to ensure that only qualified and competent candidates are appointed. This can be achieved through the Governing Council and the Human Resource Department, which should adopt clear recruitment guidelines emphasizing academic qualifications, professional competence, and experience as key criteria. This will promote fairness, transparency, and accountability in recruitment, thereby restoring public confidence in the integrity of the institution's personnel management system. The Ministry of Tertiary Education and the Office of the Head of Service should strengthen the existing legal and policy frameworks governing staff recruitment to reduce undue political influence. Recruitment processes should be guided strictly by civil service rules and institutional regulations. This will help prevent political actors from manipulating employment procedures for personal or partisan interests. The Rectory should ensure administrative autonomy and transparency by allowing recruitment committees to function independently without external interference.

Regular publication of recruitment procedures, shortlisted candidates, and final selections should be made public to enhance openness and deter political manipulation. The Internal Quality Assurance Unit and Audit Department should monitor and report any breaches of due process during staff appointments. In addition, the Staff Training and Development Unit, in partnership with the Office of Establishment and Training, should organize capacity-building and professional development programs to improve the efficiency and performance of employees. This will help bridge the competence gap caused by politically motivated recruitment and promote productivity and service delivery. The Public Service Commission and the Institutional Governing Council establish a Recruitment Oversight Committee responsible for enforcing ethical standards and monitoring compliance with recruitment regulations. This committee should include

representatives from the Academic Staff Union, Non-Academic Staff Union, and Student Affairs Division to ensure broad accountability and inclusiveness in the process. The Rectory and Human Resource Department should implement performance-based evaluation and reward systems to encourage merit and discourage mediocrity. Staff promotion and retention should be based on measurable performance indicators rather than political affiliation.

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